

FOOD QUALITY AND TOURIST SATISFACTION IN TIOMAN ISLAND

Mohd Farid Shamsudin¹, SyafiqahMd Nayan², Mohd Fikri Ishak³, Siti Aisyah Esa⁴, Sallaudin Hassan⁵

^{1,2,3,4,5}Universiti Kuala Lumpur

E-mail: mfarid@unikl.edu.my¹, syafiqah.nayan10@s.unikl.edu.my², fikri.ishak@t.unikl.edu.my³, siti.aisyah@t.unikl.edu.my⁴, sallaudin@unikl.edu.my⁵

ABSTRACT: Food quality has become essential and requirements among the customers. Today, the customer is concern about their health and wellbeing. The purpose of this research is to evaluate the roles of food quality among the customers towards satisfaction. Food quality divided into two main dimensions, which are extrinsic and intrinsic. Extrinsic is more related to external parts such as branding, regulations, and after-sales services. Intrinsic factors are more related to taste, odor, and shape, and nutritional. The research used a quantitative method where questionnaires were used to collect data. Three hundred respondents were targeted, but only 246 usable data received within the time allocated. The results indicate that both extrinsic and intrinsic were equally crucial from the customer perspective. Customer is concerned about food safety. At the same time, service providers need to put more effort into meeting customer requirements and needs.

KEYWORDS: food safety, extrinsic, intrinsic, satisfaction

I. INTRODUCTION

Tioman island is one of the famous islands in Malaysia, located in the state of Pahang. Tioman Island is famous for dive and snorkel activities, and at the same time, it is also a duty-free island[1]. Visitors to Tioman Island every year are not less than 250,000 visitors, as per figure 1 below.

Figure 1: Visitors to Tioman Island from 2010 - 2018

Source: Pahang Tourism (2019)

Visitors to Tioman island mix domestic and international with a few from ASEAN countries[2]. On the average majority of tourist were from as compared to international as per figure 2 below:

Figure 2: Visitors to Tioman Island by categories as at 2019

Overall, there are more than 50 leading tourism providers in Tioman Island with their readiness to provide their services according to customer needs and wants.

Research indicates that there are many types of tourists, and regardless of their attentions, food is necessary and essential to be considered [1]. Domestic tourist to Tioman Island is not only coming for sea sports activities but also to enjoy the food offered by the food and beverages industry in Tioman. Therefore, the role of food and its quality is important as a combined element towards tourists' overall experience during their trips to Tioman.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Tourist satisfaction

The role of tourist satisfaction and customer satisfaction is not much different, as established by the past researcher [3]. Both tourist and customer have been used interchangeably to refer to the individual that subscribed or purchased something from the service providers[4]. Tourist satisfaction can only be obtained once the total service delivered to them meets or exceeds their expectations. The higher the service delivered than expectations means, the more satisfied the tourist[5]. Individual tourists perceive customer expectations. Tourists that have experienced coming to Tioman may have a different expectation either maintains or adjustable to higher or lower compared to the previous experience. Fresh tourists may make their expectations based on past tourist comments, feedback, and reviews on the tourism portal, social media, or website[6]. Such information may lead to customer expectations prior to the service delivery.

Satisfaction, although it is difficult to achieve but very meaningful towards business survival and sustainability[7]. There are too many service providers not only related to accommodations, activities, and food beverages[8]. The large numbers of industry players created a tense competition over the limited number of potential customers[9]. Service providers primarily related to food beverages must ensure that they provide high-quality service to the customer to enjoy the benefits of the satisfaction level.

Past research indicates that customer satisfaction leads to a lot more advantages to the service provider, although it is difficult to achieve[10]. Service providers at the beginning need to understand the needs of the customer and their expectations. Meeting customer expectations primarily related to food and beverages is quite impossible[11]. Each customer may come from a different background and culture in their diet and food intake. The taste and preferences from one generation to another is also different[12]. Customers from a different state in Malaysia may also lead to a different preference as they have their local favorites. To meet the expectations, the service provider needs to get more feedback, opinion, and suggestions for improvements. The service provider should also explain their service and quality to provide potential customers with some information before consumption[13]. By doing that, the customer may set their expectations suitable to the information given so that it would not go too high or under expectations. Meeting customer expectations is a serious business, as it may bring a significant impact on the service provider[14].

Marketers and scholars in marketing [15], [16] highlighted that satisfied customers might tend to return for repeat purchases. A customer that enjoyed their overall experiences according to their expectations will come back for repeat purchase. A satisfied customer will go through the customer retention cycle. According to [17], customer retention saves the service provider budget on the customer acquisition campaign. It was mentioned by [18] that keeping a current customer is 7 to 10 times cheaper than getting a new one. It was also stated [19] that retention customers will spend 25% more than regular customers. It means that once the customer got satisfied, they will spend more money on the service providers, and keeping them is as good as to get new

acquisitions[20]. As customer returns for repeat purchases, they will spend and explore many other menu or services that available for them to consume. The service provider's challenge is to keep the consistency on the service delivery and the overall experiences [17]. A service provider that managed to remain consistent by delivering the same customer experiences over time may convert the customer to become loyal [14].

Most recent findings related to customer satisfaction [12] revealed that today's customers are fond of sharing their experiences through social media. The experiences sharing directly provide advantages to the service provider in terms of brand image and awareness. A satisfied customer will typically use social media to upload their photos and share their moments with their social networking[5]. The effect of electronic word of mouth is more effective compared to the traditional word of mouth. In the past, it was recorded that each satisfied customer will have communicated to 8 to 10 customers about their experiences, and the next people who received the information will also to the same numbers of people [21]. Social media using the internet spread even faster than word of mouth. The coverage is unlimited subject to customer intentions. It may reach the whole world as fast as a lifetime. Positive information about the service provider will bring a positive impact. Customers relied pretty much on testimonial and recommendation from their friends instead of the advertisements made by service providers[22]. Positive communication through social media will increase brand visibility and attract more customers to enjoy their services [23].

Customer satisfaction helps protect service provider market growth as the customer will not easily change their minds over the competitor offerings. Satisfied customers keep competitors away from them [24]. It was also highlighted by [13] that the satisfied customer is insensitive to price changes[14]. A slight increase in the price will not make them run away. Satisfied customers value the services more than the price. Service providers, at the same time, can have direct access to communication with customers. The service provider can have explained to customers the reason why the price needs to be increased [9]. A satisfied customer can easily be reachable, and they are willing to provide feedback to the service provider. The feedback is vital as it comes from the perspectives of the customer. The service provider needs to carefully understand the issues and make some improvements for better future services.

It has been said that customer satisfaction is not only helping the service provider to improve their business performance but helps to increase market growth[25]. Market growth derived from increased customers due to a positive brand image supported by recommendations, referrals, and testimonial by past customers[10]. The more satisfied customer, the high chance that the service provider will enjoy in terms of market growth. High results of market growth will eventually lead to a positive profit for the service providers.

2.2 Food quality

Awareness of the food quality raised among the current gen Y consumer. They have access to the information and concerns about their health more than the previous generation. Such development is proper but requires the service provider to change along with the needs, wants, and demands of the current customer. By definition, food quality refers "to the totality of characteristics of the food, that bear on its ability to satisfy stated or implied preferences. Quality implies variety and is a multidimensional concept, most of which are subjective" [26].

Food quality from the customer perspectives is about how the acceptance level of customer of the food delivery. It is about whether the food quality presented by the service provider is meeting the customer's needs and wants. [27] also mentioned that the food quality is also referring to the perceived value for money [28]. Customers will make a comparison between their expectations against the post consume experiences. The higher is the benefits of consuming means, and the higher is the customer value for money. The service provider needs to ensure that the benefits provided or supplied are higher than the amount of money that customer needs to pay in the exchange process.

At the same time, service providers must ensure that the food beverages services met and conform with the customer specifications[29]. Meeting customer needs is essential but must according to the requirements and details of what the customer needs. The conformations partly can be referred to as the local regulations set by the government authorities. Particular food has been regulated in terms of the contents if coloring and additive [29]. It should be according to the rules, especially related to the halal requirements. The majority of the population are Muslim, and the service provider needs to ensure the food supplied to meet the necessary standards requirements [27]. A service provider that enables to meet the customer expectations will enjoy customer satisfaction and eventually make more money from the profits.

Food quality is very much depending on the food quality attributes, which covers many aspects that service providers may focus on in their service delivery. Among the essential things are the external factors that refer to the shape, size, coloring, and consistency. Service providers must ensure that food quality follows the essential

characteristics in terms of size. Each product has been served according to the regulations. For example, skim milk should only contain 50% fat and not more. Service providers need to follow the recommendations in order to meet quality standards. Food quality is also related to the textures of the food delivered. An example of textures is greasy or oily and fatty. It can also be in terms of crispy, tough, and tender. Some food may have related to a different texture, such as smooth, chewy, and creamy. All types of textures are essential for the service provider to match the outcome to meet customer expectations.

Past research also indicates the importance of flavor, such as odor and taste in food quality. Odor can be explained by how the customer prescribed the smell, such as fragrant, smelly, and stinking. It depends on how customers perceived the smell. Taste in food quality is related to the overall experiences of bitter, tasteless, sweet, juicy, spicy, hot, sour, and salty. The level of taste could differentiate between one to another, but the service provider must ensure that it meets customer expectations.

Food quality is also referring to the correct labeling of the products. The products should provide enough necessary information about the ingredients, nutrients, and details of the manufacturer and supplier. Such information has been made compulsory by the regulators as part of their enforcement and tracking purposes. It was recommended that the products be wrapped, packaged, or appropriately sealed to maintain the freshness and avoid contamination. According to [28], contamination in food could be derived from a few occasions, such as physical contamination, chemical contamination, and microbiological contamination. Each category may lead to a severe health problem for the user.

Another important information that the current customer is concerned about is the amount of added flavors, added colors, antioxidants, or preservatives used in the standard food. The supplier or manufacturer should make the information clear at the label beside the recommendations of nutrition information. Information should be made in detail, such as the contents of nutrition per serving and packet—customer than can have more information and hence make a wise decision on their selection of food.

Food quality today has provided more detailed information and requirements up to the level of food traceability. The details of its origin will be recorded and kept should there be a need to recall unexpected things. Customers today are fortunate as they may have enjoyed high-quality food and, as such, make them healthier.

The service provider should conduct market sense in identifying the change of customer taste and preferences. The service provider should change their culture towards market-driven. They should gather more information about what the customer needs and how it can be fulfilling. The service provider needs to play a proactive role in meeting customer needs and expectations. Get the employee to ask a customer more details by applying adaptive customer service. Employees in food and beverages cannot treat a customer in a standard way. That is because each customer may have different needs and wants. Adaptive marketing may be able to gain more satisfaction level as they have the chance to ask what actually customer is looking for and so that they can customize the services according to the needs.

III. METHODOLOGY

This research is about to measure the relationship between extrinsic and intrinsic of food quality towards customer satisfaction. There are two primary constructs to be tested against the tourist satisfaction. This research used a quantitative method and, as such, a questionnaire to collect data. Data were collected from customers only voluntarily. Interested customers may participate in the data collection after they had their meal at the selected restaurants. The questionnaire was distributed with the help of the restaurants’ employees. Three hundred questionnaires distributed over 30 selected restaurants. Only 246 questionnaire returns, which brings to 82% return rates. There are altogether 21 questions, including the respondent details. The data were analyzed using AMOS SEM.

IV. FINDINGS

Table 1: Descriptive statistics and results of confirmatory factor analysis

Item	Mean	Sd	SFL	t-value	CR	AVE	α
Extrinsic factors							
ET 1	4.31	0.61	0.861	10.955	0.821	0.72	0.845
ET 2	4.32	0.62	0.834	10.988			
ET 3	4.44	0.64	0.822	10.935			
ET 4	3.91	0.65	0.856	10.948			
ET 5	3.85	0.67	0.851	10.995			
ET 6	4.15	0.61	0.845	10.928			
ET 7	4.15	0.61	0.845	10.928			

ET9	4.36	0.60	0.876	10.144			
ET 10	4.58	0.64	0.846	10.246			
ET 11	4.16	0.62	0.867	10.324			
ET 12	4.75	0.61	0.831	10.236			
ET 13	4.91	0.66	0.837	10.165			
Intrinsic factors							
IT 1	4.53	0.72	0.876	13.320	0.907	0.69	0.911
IT 2	4.55	0.61	0.846	12.668			
IT 3	4.29	0.74	0.838	12.564			
IT 4	4.35	0.72	0.829	12.985			
IT 7	4.25	0.77	0.818	13.680			
IT 8	4.25	0.71	0.869	12.698			
IT 9	4.75	0.78	0.851	12.554			
IT 10	4.31	0.71	0.870	12.935			
IT 11	3.90	0.70	0.853	12.634			
IT 12	3.78	0.62	0.862	12.345			
Customer satisfaction							
CS 1	4.31	0.61	0.810	12.341	0.934	0.79	0.915
CS 2	3.91	0.64	0.822	11.487			
CS 5	4.55	0.76	0.831	10.398			
CS 6	4.25	0.77	0.823	12.779			
CS 7	3.80	0.67	0.898	12.852			
Notes: SFL, standardized factor loadings; CR, composite reliability; AVE, average variance extracted; α , Cronbach's α							

Table 1 indicates that all factors loading of all items were more than the cut of acceptable value (0.70). The mean ranges for extrinsic factors are between 3.58 and 4.91. The mean for Intrinsic factors is between 3.78 and 4.75. in contrast, the mean for customer satisfaction is between 3.80 and 4.55. A few items were deleted due to poor value. Items ET 6 and ET 8 were deleted as well as IT 5, IT 6, IT 13, and IT 14. Two items from tourist satisfaction were deleted TS 3 and TS 4. Upon deletion, the items for extrinsic factors left only 11 items for Intrinsic factors left ten, and finally, the items for tourist satisfaction is 5. The Cronbach's α value is as per details in the table. The alpha value for extrinsic factors, intrinsic factors, and customer satisfaction is 0.845, 0.911, and 0.915. The average variances extracted (AVE) of the constructs ranging from 0.69 to 0.79 were higher than the minimum accepted value of 0.5 (Bagozzi and Yi, 1988).

Table 2: Squared correlations matrix of latent variables

Constructs	Mean	Extrinsic factors	Intrinsic factors	Tourist satisfaction
Extrinsic factors	4.22	0.85 ^a		
Intrinsic factors	4.42	0.76 ^b	0.69	
Tourist satisfaction	4.26	0.89	0.68	0.63
Notes: ^a Average variance extracted; ^b squared correlations				

Figure 1: Results of the hypothesized model

Notes: Standard coefficient (t-value): solid line: significant path
 ***p<0.001

The constructs and the hypothesized relationships were tested using a structural model. Figure 1 shows that extrinsic factors have a positive effect on tourist satisfaction ($\beta = 0.365$, $t = 2.654$, $p < 0.001$). Thus, H1 is supported. Intrinsic factors also positively influence tourist satisfaction ($\beta = 0.323$, $t = 2.677$, $p < 0.001$). Hence, H2 is supported. The results indicate that extrinsic and intrinsic are equally important towards tourist satisfaction with regards to the food quality.

V. DISCUSSIONS

The result indicates that both dimensions in food quality positively influence customer satisfaction. The consumer in the 21st century is getting more complicated. They have high awareness and knowledge. At the same time, according to [30], young generations are very concerns about their food quality. Extrinsic generally covers the regulation parts, price, brand name, convenience level, and as well as after-sales service. Intrinsic, on the other side, are concerns about taste, flavor, shape, nutritional, safety, and packaging. It means that the customer is looking forward to a complete package about food safety.

The results should be given priority among the food providers in preparing themselves to be more alert about the current customer's trend and needs. As the generations change, the pattern and demand for curtains products vary according to the current buying power. Therefore, food providers should get ready to meet the customers' needs and want for business survival and profitability.

VI. REFERENCES

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